

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Sustrans

Towards Equitable
Walking and Cycling
Infrastructure for All

Supported by data and
advice from Sustrans

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

This investigation was undertaken with data and advice provided by Sustrans — a UK-based charity which aims to make it easier for people to undertake active travel modes such as walking and cycling. Sustrans undertakes various initiatives and projects to achieve its objectives, including:

1. **National Cycle Network:** Sustrans developed the National Cycle Network — a network of walking and cycling routes that spans the UK; they now act as custodians for the network. The network aims to provide safe and convenient routes for active travel, connecting communities, urban areas, and rural regions.
2. **Promotion of Active Travel:** Sustrans promotes walking and cycling as viable transportation options through campaigns, educational programs, and awareness-raising initiatives. The organisation encourages individuals to choose active modes of travel for their daily commutes, leisure activities, and local journeys.
3. **Infrastructure Development:** Sustrans advocates for the development of cycling and walking infrastructure across the UK. This involves working with local authorities, communities, and stakeholders to improve and expand networks of dedicated paths, lanes, and facilities for pedestrians and cyclists.
4. **Policy and Advocacy:** Sustrans engages in policy development and advocacy efforts at national and local levels to shape transportation policies and infrastructure investments that prioritise sustainable travel options.
5. **Research and Evaluation:** Sustrans conducts research and evaluation studies to understand the impact of active travel and sustainable transportation on health, the environment, and communities. The findings contribute to evidence-based approaches and help inform future initiatives and projects.

This investigation focuses on the first of these initiatives — the National Cycle Network. This investigation aims to provide an improved

understanding of how accessible the National Cycle Network (NCN) is to its users, and the types of people who use it to make access more equitable.

1.2 Main objectives

As outlined in Section 1.1, Sustrans have a series of projects and initiatives; these include acting as custodians for the National Cycle Network, and undertaking research and evaluation. As such, they aim to evaluate how the network is used, by whom and the extent to which access to the network is equitable. One of the key concepts underpinning the evaluation of network accessibility is that of spatial buffers. In the context of spatial statistics, a buffer is a zone or area around a geographic feature (e.g. a point, line, or polygon). The buffer is defined by a specified distance or radius, and all points within that distance are considered to be within the buffer zone [Smith et al., 2007]. Buffers are commonly used in spatial analysis to identify features that fall within a certain distance of other features, or to create a visual representation of the area that is affected by a particular feature. Such buffers allow us to identify regions which are adjacent to the network.

With this in mind, the initial objectives of the investigation were as follows:

1. Develop a buffer, covering sections of the street network around access points on the NCN that takes into account different measures of distance.
2. Develop a novel method for defining a realistic geospatial buffer around the NCN that identifies who has access, taking into account the location of access points. Ideally, this method would also be applicable to points and polygons.
3. Undertake an analysis of the relationship between the provision of infrastructure on the NCN, the way in which the network is used, and the impact of demographic factors on this relationship.
4. Develop improved methods for estimating whole-network usage based on local count data.

5. Explore spatiotemporal patterns in network usage.
6. Identify informal access points through satellite imaging (paths through the grass, holes in hedges, etc.).

In particular, this investigation has focused on [Objective 1](#), [Objective 2](#), [Objective 3](#), [Objective 4](#) and [Objective 5](#). Some preliminary work was undertaken towards scoping an approach for [Objective 6](#), and some suggestions were provided for how this might be taken forward.

1.3 Data overview

For this investigation, data from multiple sources were used. The following central datasets were provided by Sustrans:

- Geospatial data that represent the NCN network of cycling and walking routes across the United Kingdom;
- Internal estimates of NCN usage based on population estimates close to the network;
- Time-series count data of the number of users observed at a variety of locations across the network; and
- Responses from surveys of users of the network.

The geospatial NCN data underpin much of the work undertaken in this investigation and were used to address [Objective 1](#) to [Objective 5](#), as well as to explore initial approaches to [Objective 6](#). The internal estimates of usage of the National Cycle Network were used to address [Objective 3](#) and [Objective 4](#). The time-series count data were used to address [Objective 5](#). The survey responses were used to address [Objective 3](#).

In addition a collection of open-source datasets were used; these consisted of data mapping data from OpenStreetMap and demographic data from the UK Census. As with the geospatial NCN data, these datasets also underpinned much of this investigation.

1.4 Approach

In order to address the objectives outlined in Section 1.2, a collection of different approaches were applied.

Much of this investigation was underpinned by spatial datasets which were provided as different spatial resolutions. In order to combine and make use of these datasets, spatial joins were employed. Much like conventional data joins, spatial joins seek to combine the columns of one datasets with the columns of another based on some shared variable. In conventional data joins, datasets are often combined based on shared index or variable; in spatial joins, however, datasets are combined based on how they spatially intersect each other.

To address [Objective 1](#), geospatial methods were used which allowed for the joining of spatial datasets such as the National Cycle Network data and the OpenStreetMap data. This allowed the identification of sections of the road network (detailed in the OpenStreetMap data) which are directly connected to the National Cycle Network. Points where the two networks intersect were identified as access points for the National Cycle Network, around which buffers were drawn based on Euclidean distance from the access points.

Based on this, network methods were used to address [Objective 2](#) by defining a network-based approach to drawing access buffers based on the identified access points. This involved defining buffers based on network distances using Dijkstra's algorithm instead of Euclidean distances.

Additionally, using spatial methods to join the outputs of [Objective 1](#) and [Objective 2](#) with the survey data and time-series count data allowed us to explore how temporal usage patterns were influenced by infrastructure and demographics, thereby addressing [Objective 3](#).

[Objective 4](#) was addressed through the use of dimensionality reduction methods, regression methods and spatial joins, exploring how network usage estimates varied with various network attributes.

In order to address [Objective 5](#), the counter data was used in conjunction with the layout of the NCN; this allowed us to explore the temporal variation of volumes of users on the network at different temporal resolution.

1.5 Main conclusions

The results of this investigation consist of a collection of novel methods that may be used to address future problems and a set of evidence-based conclusions which may inform subsequent investigations.

In addressing [Objective 1](#) and [Objective 2](#), we have developed methods to identify formal access points to the National Cycle Network and have developed a novel approach to drawing spatial access buffers around it. Improved approaches to drawing buffers around the network allow us to more accurately capture which households reside within a given distance of the network, i.e. which households have access to it. By exploring the demographics of the populations who dwell at these households, we can provide a more accurate picture of the demographics of those who have easy access to the network. This has culminated in the proposal of a general workflow to explore how different demographic factors interact with network accessibility.

In addressing [Objective 3](#), [Objective 4](#) and [Objective 5](#), we have explored how the network is used, who it is used by and how usage is impacted by different network attributes. It was found that usage of the network varied temporally at different temporal resolutions. When considering usage at an hourly level, it was found that commuting patterns on weekdays had bimodal distributions, resulting in peak usage during the morning rush-hour and evening rush-hour. Usage on weekends tended to be uni-modal with usage occurring during mid-day. When considering usage at a monthly level, it was found that the network was more heavily used in summer months. These relationships were mediated by network attributes such as lighting and surface quality; the provision of lighting correlated with increased usage, as did the provision of higher quality surfaces.

1.6 Limitations

The methods and conclusions detailed above have several limitations. The method developed for drawing spatial access buffers around the National Cycle Network does so by identifying regions that are within a fixed network distance of access points on the network. People's views of accessibility may not, however, be based on distance but instead on travel

time. The approach outlined here essentially assumes a fixed walking/cycling speed for all uses of the network and so uses a fixed network distance around the access points. A further improvement to the method could be to take into account the demographics of the population around the access points (e.g., the proportion of older adults) so as to inform the calculation of the buffer.

Additionally, when considering the time-series data produced by the counters we observed that the datastreams at some of the counters are not continuous (i.e., some counters produce time-series with sections of missing values). This has made it difficult to perform more advanced time-series analysis and comparison of datastreams between different sensors.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

Part of this work has focused on the identification of formal access points, i.e., points where people can access the National Cycle Network directly from other road networks and paths. A further objective — [Objective 6](#) — was suggested with the hope of identifying informal access points where people do not use intersections of the network with roads or paths but access it in some other way. We suggest two potential approaches to achieving this:

- Use of heatmaps of individual-level trajectories; and
- Use of satellite imagery.

Additionally, we suggest the use of agent-based modelling to explore the potential impact of future changes to infrastructure, particularly when planning to develop new routes which may divert cyclists away from roads. Given that one of Sustrans' priorities is to ensure that active travel infrastructure is developed in an equitable manner, this would be beneficial as it would provide an artificial test-bed to simulate changes and provide disaggregated information about the changes in individual-level behaviour resulting from changes in policy and infrastructure. This would then allow us to anticipate how different demographic groups would be impacted by these changes.

2 Data overview

This section seeks to provide an overview of the data used in this investigation. This includes a description of the various datasets (Section 2.1) as well as a brief discussion of some of the data quality issues and challenges that were encountered (Section 2.3). Some of the data used in this investigation were provided by Sustrans; these datasets included National Cycle Network data, Whole Network Usage Estimate data, Counter data and data from the Route User Intercept Survey. Additionally, other open data sources were used such as data from OpenStreetMap (OSM). Several of these data sets were expanded upon by participants enhancing the data in terms of geo-precision, spatial-temporal analysis, and node analysis (as detailed in Section 3).

2.1 Dataset description

This section focuses specifically on what information each dataset contains, how they were provided and by whom. This covers data provided by Sustrans as well as open datasets that were identified over the course of the investigation.

2.1.1 National Cycle Network

The National Cycle Network data was provided by Sustrans as a shapefile. In this dataset, each record corresponded to a small line segments making up part of the network and had a ID (labelled as FID) as a unique identifier; line segments are described as polylines (i.e., vectors of coordinates). Additional features were available describing the surface condition, lighting conditions, whether the part was on-road etc. Records were partitioned when these features changed. The data is openly available through the [Sustrans ArcGIS webportal](#), as well as through an API (although this was not used for this investigation).

2.1.2 OpenStreetMap

The OpenStreetMaps ecosystem provides free and publicly available mapping data, including layers of data for routing [Bennett, 2010], i.e. data which is used to help end-users to navigate a route from one place to another. Such routing choices depend on a number of factors such as highway type, number of lanes, highway condition, the presence of crossing and junctions and average speed. These layers are, therefore, a rich source of information. The Python `osmnx` package [Boeing, 2017] was used to download map data (via an API) for areas of interest, which were typically those around identified NCN routes. In order to achieve this, a buffer of around 100 metres was added to the routes to facilitate processing. For example, if we wish to trace streets up to 500m around a NCN route we might download all streets within 600m of that route.

Downloading OpenStreetMaps data for whole areas (such as UK cities) is very time consuming and thus presents a bottleneck in most geospatial analyses related to the NCN. A considerable speedup can be achieved by defining an area around the NCN in the geography of interest (Upper Tier Local Authority in the analysis below) and a 'buffer region' around the NCN in that area. The OSM data in that buffer region can then be downloaded and stored to be re-used in later processes. A tool was created to enable this. A bug was found where the download would only process one component if the provided region was not contiguous. We designed the tool to break regions into contiguous spatial components, download and combine the maps for those regions (accounting for overlaps). To decrease the computational time required, this process was run in parallel without incurring any rate-limiting.

2.1.3 Census data

UK Census data was taken from both 2011 and 2021 and was used to measure demographic differences, gain a deeper understanding of geographic boundaries, and gauge accessibility for cycle path users in terms of housing connectivity to access points which is assessed by considering the distances between houses and access points on the network. Census data was available with aggregate counts of either the number of residents or households at Output Area (OA) level — this level

of geography tends to capture areas of 100-625 people. A mapping table was used to convert data for 2011 OAs to 2021 OAs. This was downloaded in .csv format at Output Area (OA) level ¹ from [NOMIS](#). This mapping reflects changes in Census geographies that occurred between 2011 and 2021 as a result of population and household changes ².

To identify output areas relevant to a specific analysis, geographies were joined using an 'intersects' spatial join to the output area polygon, which may increase numbers associated with any geography being analysed. An alternative choice would have been to join with the output area centroid and to require this to be contained within a region analysed, but this can lead to regions not associated with any output area. This occurs when none of the output areas' centroids lie within the region analysed (e.g., within a buffer around the National Cycle Network).

2.1.4 Counter data

A dataset that contains the count of cyclists and pedestrians on an hourly basis at locations on the NCN was provided by Sustrans. The dataset covers the years 2015-2022, providing information for both cyclist and pedestrian counts. The counter dataset can be linked to the corresponding owner IDs and coordinates of the counter in a corresponding information file through the unique counter ID. In this dataset, counts that are considered erroneous based on visual checks have been excluded in collaboration with the data providers.

2.1.5 Department for Transport counter data

Counter data from the Department for Transport is available to download from the Department for Transport's website. The Annual Average Daily Flow (AADF) Data was provided for the challenge. The AADF data provides the number of vehicles categorised by vehicle type (including cyclists) that pass the count point (in both directions) on an average day of the year. The dataset covers the years 2000-2021.

¹Output areas are small geographies generally containing between 100 and 625 people, allowing for very specific breakdowns of the country.

²Details regarding changes to Census geographies in 2021 can be found [here](#)

2.1.6 Route user intercept survey data

The Route User Intercept Survey (RUIS) data provides details of surveyed users of the network, collected over several years. It contains rich information on their trip purposes, modes, and various spatial and demographic details. Additionally, it also records the users' ease of accessibility to different resources over these years, which was useful to compare user populations of the network.

2.1.7 Whole network usage estimates data

The Whole Network Usage Estimate (WNUE) data provides network usage estimates for the national cycle network from 2019-2021. The NCN is divided into sections $\leq 1\text{km}$ and the midpoints for these sections are the geographical coordinates that could be spatially joined with other datasets such as NCN or counter data. The usage of monitored sections is calculated either through automatic counters or manual calculation by the Department of Traffic Control. The data from the monitored sections are used to estimate the usage of non-monitored sections. The dataset has usage-determining characteristics such as the population around each area, whether the section is on the road or off-road, the level of cycling to work, and cycling and pedestrian usage on the NCN.

Note this uses population-weighted centroids for the adjacent geometries when calculating the population gravity for sections, i.e., it uses the point within the geographical area that represents the centre of the area based on how the population is distributed within it. In some cases, the centroid may lie outside of the buffer around network sections; this does not necessarily mean that none of the population from a geometry reside within the buffer, only that the centroid itself does not reside within the buffer. This may mean that the usage estimates in some areas may be lower than expected.

WNUE data is similar to the counter data in that it includes some (inconsistent) section IDs. It may be better to rely on the midpoint to map it and overlay on NCN.

2.2 Data visualisation

In this section, we provide some initial visualisations of the datasets provided. Given the spatial nature of the data, this allows us to provide an overview of the layout of the network and how the other datasources relate to it.

2.2.1 Location of the National Cycle Network, counters and route user intercept surveys

Figure 1 contains a map of the outline of the National Cycle Network overlaid with the point locations of counters provided by Sustrans and DfT, plus locations of route user intercept surveys. Only DfT counters on the NCN have been displayed; in addition to those illustrated here, a number of DfT counters can be found in locations that do not lie on the NCN. The map illustrates, for example, that there is no coverage of counters and surveys in Northern Ireland, limited coverage in Wales and dense coverage around Glasgow and Edinburgh. The lack of data coverage in Northern Island is outlined in Section 2.3.5.

2.2.2 Whole network usage estimates

As outlined in Section 2.3.6, one of the variables in the estimates — the estimated pedestrian trips — contained a large proportion of missing values and as such only the remaining three variables were used for this investigation. Figure 2 shows the scatterplots for the three numerical columns. Figure 2a shows the relationship between the logarithm of predicted cycle trips and the cycle to work gravity in the area. We see a few outliers in this representation; the connection is not strictly linear. The majority of the data points represent a relatively low cycle-to-work gravity of ≤ 0.4 ; as the frequency of cycling to work increases, the number of cycle trips taken follows a logarithmic pattern. The same is true for the Figure 2b, where the number of cycle trips logarithmically increases with the population gravity of the area. Figure 2c shows the correlation between the population gravity and cycle-to-work gravity. Most points are clustered in the lower left quadrant, suggesting a correlation between lower population density and lower frequency of cycling to work.

Figure 1: Outline of data on the National Cycle Network; blue lines show sections of the National Cycle Network, black points show locations of counters, purple points show locations where surveys were undertaken, and pink points show locations of DfT counters.

(a) Logarithmic variation of Predicted Cycling Trips with Cycle to Work

(b) Logarithmic variation of Predicted Cycle trips with Population Gravity

(c) Variation of Cycle to Work with Population Gravity of the section

Figure 2: Scatterplots for the relationship between numerical parameters of network usage estimation.

(a) Logarithmic frequency of Predicted Cycling Trips with the NCN Surface

(b) Logarithmic variation of Predicted Cycle Trips with the NCN Quality

(c) Logarithmic Variation of Predicted Cycle Trips with the NCN Lighting

Figure 3: Frequency distribution of predicted cycle trips as a measure of usage based on characteristics of the NCN - Surface, Quality and Lighting.

To analyse the impact of NCN characteristics on the network usage statistics, we conducted a spatial join on the NCN and WNUE data. The resulting join provides us with various categorical variables for the NCN, and we excluded columns with high missing values ($> 50\%$). Subsequently, we plotted the frequency distribution in Figure 3 for the following variables:

- Type of Surface: There are several kinds of surface - Asphalt, Unsealed Firm, Blocks, Pavement Slab, Grass, Concrete, Bare Earth, Cobbles and Rocky.
- Quality of Surface: The surface quality states whether it is smooth, well maintained, or of standard or acceptable quality.
- Lighting on Surface: Path lighting has three factors - whether it is fully lit, partly lit or unlit.

To improve data visualisation, we transformed the count to a logarithmic scale; this allows us to observe how some categories in the data occur orders of magnitude more frequently than others. Upon examining the frequency distribution plots for the type of surface in Figure 3a and path quality in Figure 3b we noted that the majority of the surfaces were made of asphalt and most paths were rated as standard or acceptable in quality. Upon examining the distributions of area lighting in the Figure 3c, it was also evident that the vast majority of the surfaces were not equipped with lighting.

Figures 4 and 5 show the availability of network usage statistics superimposed on the NCN map. In Figure 4, it can be observed that the NCN had the highest coverage in 2019, which decreased in 2020 and further decreased in 2021. Additionally, the paths on the NCN undergo changes each year, with some being added and others being removed. Despite this, the quality of the NCN has improved.

Figure 5 illustrates the on-road and off-road sections of the WNUE superimposed on the NCN. Notably, the left portion of the map representing Northern Ireland contains only off-road sections. Comparing this with Figure 4, we observe that much of this section is no longer part of the NCN. Overall, the off-road sections appear more prevalent than the on-road ones.

Figure 4: Year-wise variation of the network usage superimposed on the NCN.

Figure 5: Outline of on- and off-road sections of the NCN

2.2.3 Route User Intercept Survey data for individual trips

As part of the survey, respondents were asked about the purpose of their trip and the activity they were out for. This data shows the representation of all the participants who were approached for the surveys, and demonstrates possible biases which might have impacted on the surveys conducted.

Figure 6: Variation in frequency of trip purpose by age and gender; left to right — male, female, other/undisclosed.

Figure 6 shows the purpose of the trips for each participant. In these figures, we observe that the line pertaining to leisure (i.e. the blue line) was higher than other lines for all age brackets and all genders. This indicates that the majority of the respondents were using the NCN for leisure activities; this was the case for each of the gender groups and age groups. Furthermore, we can observe that in the case of each of the genders, older generations accounted for a large portion of respondents. It can also be seen that in general, there were more male respondents than female respondents. This could account for some level of data bias. This bias (i.e., the large proportion of respondents being from older generations and undertaking leisure activities) may not be due to the lack of people from other groups undertaking different activities, but instead due to the engagement time required to participate in the survey — individuals undertaking trips for other purposes may not have time to engage in the survey.

Figure 7: Variation in frequency of trip activities by age and gender; left to right — male, female, other/undisclosed.

Figure 7 corroborates some of the findings from Figure 6 regarding the gender and age balance of the respondents. In addition, this figure shows that across each of the age brackets and genders, respondents were more often pedestrians than cyclists (or undertaking another activity). Based on these findings, we should be cautious of demographic biases in the data. A future area of research could be to ensure a comparable proportion of representation among various demographics to eliminate biases.

2.3 Data quality issues and challenges

In this section, we detail the data quality issues that were encountered over the course of the DSG. In addition, we attempt to provide an overview of some measures that may be used to overcome these challenges.

2.3.1 Analysis of geospatial data

Most geospatial data used in this analysis comes in tabular format, where some of the columns correspond to geometries - these correspond to points, lines, polygons or combinations thereof on the surface of the Earth (in our case the British Isles). These can come in different coordinate systems, such as latitude and longitude (which is a degree-based system) and eastings and northings (which is a metre-based system, as is the UK National Grid). Latitude/longitude is used to download records from OpenStreetMap data and metre-based systems for calculating distances (and expanding buffer zones) and areas.

As datasets can have slightly different sources of coordinates and often mismatch in other ways - for instance the NCN record of a road will try to

follow the cycle path down one side of the road, which will not exactly match the OpenStreetMap path corresponding to the road, as these are often gathered from individual traces (which will exhibit noise) and will often follow car paths or the middle of the road. There can also be small amounts of noise or rounding errors which will make it unlikely for points to exactly sit on lines. These discrepancies can be seen in Figure 8. This is compensated for by adding buffer zones — in this work that has typically been 10m — to geometries prior to using spatial joins to compensate for such error. Spatial joins are equivalent to standard relational joins but consider relations between geometries such as ‘intersects’ and ‘contains’ [Campbell and Shin, 2011]. When considering two geometries, A and B , we say that A contains B if the entire area of B lies within area of geometry A . We can similarly say that A and B intersect if the areas of the two geometries overlap with each other.

Figure 8: Illustration of differences between different geospatial datasources. Red lines show the National Cycle Network; blue lines show the street and path network from OpenStreetMaps; purple shaded regions show the buffer around the NCN.

2.3.2 Consistency between datasets

The datasets used for this Data Study Group had ID numbers for different segments of the NCN that were not consistent or of a similar format to the other datasets. Recommendations on improving the consistency of ID numbers have been made in Section 4.1.

2.3.3 Counter data

The counter data is provided for the years 2015 through 2022. Individual counter data may not be continuous throughout this time period which would limit temporal analysis.

At some counter stations, the daily count volume appears to be inputted at 00:00 of that day. Care therefore needs to be taken to exclude these; this is achieved by removing hourly count volumes recorded at 00:00 for each counter.

2.3.4 RUIS data

Though the dataset and the metadata were comprehensive, some key quality issues were noted:

- **Non-standardised data collection format.** Because the data contained survey responses from various surveys conducted over a range of years, many of the questions were modified and adapted accordingly. This increased the level of comprehension and diversity for those questions, but also made it difficult to collate with the data collected from the previous surveys, leading to loss of information.
- **Too many variables providing the same information.** Some of the key variables of focus contained similar information, yet with different sets of labels. The labels were not clearly defined, and in some cases under-represented (i.e., less/no data points for some categories or labels).
- **Information of the time of collection of the data points.** Continuing from the previous point, the variables did not have information on when they were collected. This inhibited time-series analysis and the changes observed from there. While the dataset

had information on how many times surveys were conducted in a particular region, it lacked information on when they were made and if the time coincided with other surveys from other regions.

- **Combination of questions about individual vs general journeys.** While some questions had information on the respondent's current journey (during the survey questionnaires), some had information on the accessibility of different types of resources (e.g. education, social).

2.3.5 Spatial variation in data availability/scarcity

As shown in Section 2.2.1, the extent to which data is available varies spatially. This is driven by a variation in monitoring infrastructure. Of particular note is the difference in data availability between Northern Ireland and the other countries of the United Kingdom. This discrepancy is largely driven by the provision of funding.

In England, the Department for Transport (DfT) and the National Lottery have been funding the NCN for 30 years (as well as some other funders); often, counters and surveys are specifically undertaken where work and improvements happen. In Scotland, the government has a very strong focus on funding sustainable transport; there are plans to make a much more coherent framework across Scotland to connect smaller towns. The counters and surveys are also more strategically placed and not just based on where things are built, however, parts of Scotland are not very heavily populated. In Wales the approach is similar to Scotland; the Welsh government is committed to future generations which means they strategically spend on sustainable transport; there are key routes which are monitored but large areas which are not.

In Northern Ireland, however, both the provision and evaluation of the network are not as well funded; a lack of specific government funding means that this only happens through the National Lottery or previous EU funding.

2.3.6 Whole Network Usage Estimates missing values

The WNUE data has four numerical parameters. There are two columns for pedestrian and cyclist usage counts. The column pertaining to pedestrians has more than 50% missing values, which means that any analysis or predictions on that column would be highly inaccurate. Therefore, we did not utilise that column, which left us with three numerical columns:

- Predicted cycle trips: number of annual cycle trips from a section calculated through automatic counter, DfT data or extrapolated based on similar areas.
- Population gravity: Population density in a 10 km radius of the section mid-point weighted on the square of the distance from the point.
- Cycle to work gravity: The proportion of people cycling to work in a 10 km radius with respect to the section mid-point, weighted by the square of the distance from the point.

2.4 Data summary

This section outlines the datasets provided by Sustrans and openly available datasets that we used.

The data provided by Sustrans consists of:

- Geospatial data on the location of National Cycle Network routes (as well as information about the different attributes of segments of the network).
- Time-series counter data collected at different locations and times across the network.
- Route User Intercept Survey data which comprise survey responses from users of the NCN.
- Whole Network Usage Estimate data which provides model estimates of the level of usage across all sections of the network by making use of a combination of counter data and population data.

In addition to the Sustrans data, the following openly available datasets were used:

- OpenStreetMap data on the locations of roads and paths across the country.
- Census data which can be used to explore the demographics of population in different regions of the country.
- Geographical lookup tables which can be used to define the relationships between different spatial regions at different geographical scales.

3 Experiments and analysis

This section provides information on the analysis undertaken on the data to achieve the objectives outlined in Section 1.2.

3.1 Identifying access points to the National Cycle Network

This section outlines the approaches undertaken to identify access points to the NCN. This includes attempts to identify both formal and informal access points.

3.1.1 Formal access points

For this investigation, we define formal access points as points where a known route (footpath, road, or cycle path) which is not itself part of the network meets a section of the network of interest (which we shall refer to as a *relevant section*). Two methods were tested to identify these points. Both of the trialled methods required that the following criteria were satisfied:

- The routes that are identified are valid OpenStreetMap routes — either roads or paths.
- The route is part of a *relevant section*.

We identified OSM routes which were already part of the relevant section by taking the OSM edge list and identifying the edges which were wholly contained within a buffer around the relevant section. Based on this, we were able to identify formal access points through two approaches:

1. **Identifying OSM routes which directly intersected the relevant section (excluding those already part of the relevant section).** As the relevant section is somewhat offset from the OSM route corresponding to it, some intersections would be omitted if we only used the relevant section. Therefore we also added the OSM routes which were part of the relevant section to the relevant section itself. This produces a set of intersection points, sometimes in closely adjacent pairs due to the duplication of routes (although this is not deemed to be a problem).
2. **Adding a buffer around the relevant section and identifying OSM routes (excluding those already part of the relevant section) which intersect the buffer.** This produces a set of short line segments.

These approaches result in the points and segments found in Figure 9; the first of these approaches produces the points found in the figure, whilst the second approach produces the line segments found in the figure. Given that the two approaches identified similar locations as access points, they were both deemed to be fit-for-purpose.

Access points could then be validated by requiring that an OpenStreetMaps node be nearby. This aimed to reduce spurious intersections, such as between a cycle path going under a bridge and the road above that bridge. For the purpose of this investigation, this validation was undertaken by finding the nearest OpenStreetMaps node within 10 metres. This issue can be observed in Figure 10. In Figure 10a, we see a collection of identified access points along the NCN near the MRC Laboratory for Molecular Biology in Cambridge. The figure shows that whilst many of the identified access points passed this validation check, some did not. One such access point that failed to pass the validation test was the point identified at the Long Road Underpass; as can be seen in Figure 10b, this point is indeed not a valid access point between the NCN and the street network.

Figure 9: Access point identification. Red points show points identified by Approach 1; purple lines show segments identified by Approach 2

(a) Identified access points near overpass. Blue lines indicate sections of the National Cycle Network; yellow points indicate identified access points which are valid; red points indicate identified access points which are invalid.

(b) Google Street View of Long Road Underpass.

Figure 10: Access point validation
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3.1.2 Informal access points

We explored the potential of GPS traces to identify informal access points to the NCN that cannot be detected through footpath and road network intersections with the NCN. For example, Strava creates a global heatmap of its users public activities over the last two years [Strava, 2023]. The Strava heatmap is not open access and is likely not representative of all user of the NCN. Instead, we explored the viability of using GPS traces that are available through OSMs.

Individual public GPS traces are available to download from OSMs. The traces can be downloaded within a bounding box through the OSM API. Public traces downloaded through the API are randomised. Since GPS traces are downloaded individually, a geospatial dataset such as a heatmap would need to be created in order to use the traces for identifying informal access points. We made the decision not to take this avenue further to avoid handling data that may be identifiable.

3.2 Improving the buffer around the National Cycle Network

One key goal of the project was to improve the estimate of the area which has access to the NCN. Access is assumed to be available at a specific distance, which may vary depending on the sorts of use we are considering — walking versus cycling, for instance. Traditionally the area with access was calculated by adding a buffer zone of the appropriate distance around the NCN. This is shown in blue in Figure 11 and is a significant overestimate, particularly in rural areas where access points may be few and far between. Now that access points have been identified, an easy improvement is to instead construct the buffer zone only around the access points, as shown in purple in Figure 11. However, this still ignores the presence of obstacles such as rivers and railways which may not be traversable.

In order to address these issues, we propose the use of isochrones [O'Sullivan et al., 2000]. Isochrones are areas of uniform travel time, which can be thought of as contours on a map corresponding to a travel-time metric from an area. We can construct them by first

identifying the access points as elements of the OSM node-list, then using Dijkstra's algorithm with multiple starting points (corresponding to the identified nodes) to identify the subgraph reachable within the specific distance along appropriately traversable OSM routes. This is shown in red in the figures.

Sometimes it is important to gain an estimate of the area served, and this can be achieved by constructing a concave hull around the isochrone geometry. A hull is a polygon which contains a set of points — in this case, access points. Computationally, these are constructed by joining up areas in-between the points. In doing so, we wish to ensure that the areas highlighted do not cover areas unnecessarily, i.e., they do not suggest that areas have access to the network when they do not. In order to achieve this, we ensure that the hulls constructed are concave. Concave hulls are polygons which enclose a set of points while minimising the polygon's total area; this produces a polygon which follows the shape of the points as closely as possible [Moreira and Santos, 2007].

Partitioning the isochrone geometry first into contiguous components avoids the need for the concave hull to be connected itself; however, it can still be seen in Figure 12 that the concave hull can cover areas which may not actually be served due to its construction. Thus where possible (for instance when identifying output areas or postcode areas the NCN serves) spatial joins can be conducted with the isochrone geometry directly rather than the concave hull.

3.3 Approaches to analysing access to the network

Having devised approaches for identifying access points along the network and how buffers may take these into account, we will now go on to explore what the ramifications of these new approaches are for the accessibility of the network. In particular, we will consider this in the following ways:

- **Calculating permeability:** measure how far each stretch of the network gets from an access point.
- **Calculating inaccessibility:** given an access zone, we can take the set difference of a cycle network and a buffer around the access zone to split it into what is accessible or not.

Figure 11: The results of different buffer approaches around the NCN. Blue sections indicate a uniform buffer around the network; purple sections indicate a uniform circular buffer around access points; red lines indicate isochrones from identified access points; yellow sections indicate concave hull about the isochrones.

Figure 12: Illustration of issues with concave hulls. Note red NCN routes in top-right corner contained within blue buffer but without any yellow hull.

- **Distance measurement:** often buffer zones have been defined in degrees due to the data being in latitude/longitude scale by default. This may lead to small differences as the length corresponding to a degree varies slightly between Scotland and England.

3.3.1 Permeability metrics

The goal of permeability is to improve the safety and appeal of the network. This is a particular priority with regards to female users who are typically less likely to take active transport modes when dedicated infrastructure is not provided [Garrard et al., 2008]. Here, we define permeability as a measure of how frequently along stretches of the NCN access points are available; this may be of particular interest to people such as women for whom safety may be a priority [Cope, 2003, Aldred et al., 2017]. Such groups may feel more vulnerable on more enclosed sections of the network, such as long fenced-in paths where no escape is possible for a longer distance. The proposed way to evaluate this is to take a section of the network and look at the sizes of sections between access points — where these are too long, the section is insufficiently permeable. The metric used was to pick a threshold length (50m and 200m were chosen for the analysis as expectations and available access points are very different for urban and rural routes) and report the proportion of the route length in sections between access points above the threshold length.

This method and metric, however, has flaws. Large buffers are used around access points (10m by default, to match with the buffers used to identify and validate access points), and these are thus deducted from the length of the between-access-point sections (such as those illustrated in Figure 13), so they will not add up to the lengths of the sections in the network. This could be compensated for by using a different metric — for instance a proportion or weighted proportion (by length or utilisation) of sections which are not acceptably permeable at some parametrised length.

It should also be noted that some segments of the NCN terminate at endpoints; these endpoints may not always be accessible themselves and so when calculating permeability we may not assume that these are access points. It is, therefore, important to ensure that the segment

analysed is sufficiently large that edge conditions do not have a large bearing on the permeability calculation. In the later analysis this is achieved by looking at NCN segments at Upper Tier Local Authority (UTLA) level, where there are often hundreds of kilometres of cycle routes.

Figure 13: Partitioning routes into sections between access points.

3.3.2 Accessibility metrics

One purpose of understanding the buffer zone is to understand who may be close to the buffer zone but not able to access it. The metric used was to compute the area of the concave hull of the isochrone and use this to calculate the ratio, r , between this area and the area covered by the cruder buffer, i.e., the blue buffers displayed on Figures 11 and 12. The ratio, r , is calculated as:

$$r = \frac{A_c}{A_b}, \quad (1)$$

where A_c is the area covered by the concave hull and A_b is the area covered by the crude buffer. The result of such a calculation, r , is a

proportion of space which ranges from 0 to 1. In the case of $r = 1$, the area near the NCN covered by the crude buffer and the area covered by the isochrones are the same, showing that all of the space near the network is accessible based on the road- and path-network near the NCN. Conversely, in the case of $r \approx 0$, the area covered by the isochrone is much smaller than the area covered by the crude buffer, showing that the majority of the area near the NCN is not connected to the NCN by the road- and path-network. This aims to measure the space that is near to the cycle network based on network distance, i.e., what proportion of the space near the cycle network can actually access the network based on the current provision of infrastructure and access points?

This could be very easily improved using the existing tooling and data products by instead considering resident populations, i.e., counting people rather than space; this is particularly relevant in rural areas which may have very few residents. We may approach this using the Output Area-based methods in Section 3.3.3 (for instance) to see what Output Areas (OAs) intersect the cruder buffer zones but do not intersect the isochrone. It may be possible to be even more granular here, for instance using postcode or household/neighbourhood location data, but that would require use of more sensitive data.

3.3.3 Statistical analysis

The NCN in England and Wales was divided into Upper Tier Local Authorities (UTLAs) using ONS data ³. Segments of the route in these authorities were then categorised as either Urban or Non-Urban depending on the 2011 census classification of the majority of the residents of the 2011 output areas crossed by each segment. This breakdown is illustrated in Figure 14.

Access points which were present were identified in each UTLA (Upper Tier Local Authority) for 'urban', 'non-urban' and 'all' routes. The length of the NCN sections and distances between access points were used to calculate the proportion of the NCN in the relevant UTLA, and

³Some discrepancies were found in this data — there may have been some confusion between North Somerset and South Gloucestershire and between Swansea and Neath Port Talbot. These issues have been corrected by the ONS.

Figure 14: Urban and Non-Urban routes in England and Wales; urban routes are marked in blue and non-urban routes are marked in red.

subsequently to classify which segments were less permeable. Accessible zones were then identified around the NCN at distances of 200m (for walking) and 500m (for cycling) and assessed for accessibility. These zones were mapped to intersecting 2021 OAs to calculate the population served, along with the demographic factors relevant to cycling. For example, the proportion who were of White ethnicity, the proportion of households with a car or van and the proportion of deprived households. These proportions were then compared with the statistics of all OAs of the relevant urban/rural classification in the UTLA to evaluate whether the population served effectively represented the population of the UTLA. An example of this mapping can be found in Figure 15.

It would be possible to compute similar statistics for Scotland and Northern Ireland, particularly those around accessibility and permeability of the route. However this was not done at the time as 2021 census data was not available for these countries.

Figure 15: Illustration of demographics of population served by National Cycle Network route through Leeds (with regards to ethnicity); colour gradient indicates proportion of population identifying as white.

3.3.4 Outline of tools created

The tools created enable a workflow which takes an actual or proposed route (as a list of path segments), identifies the access points and the population served and assesses that in the context of the local area. Such a workflow is outlined in Figure 16.

Based on a route — either existing or proposed — we are able to obtain both local route geographies from OpenStreetMap and demographic information regarding the population near the route. When used in conjunction with geographic data regarding the route, the OpenStreetMap data allow us to identify formal access points (as outlined in Section 3.1.1) which subsequently allow us provide measures of route permeability (as outlined in Section 3.3.1). The identified access points also allow us to make use of our improved method for drawing buffers (see Section 3.2) to identify access zones around the route which then allow us to assess route accessibility as outlined in Section 3.3.2. The aforementioned access zones and demographic information can be used together to identify the demographics of those served by the route with the attached set of access points, allowing us to analyse the equity implications of such a route, as well as exploring how it impacts both rural and urban areas.

Figure 16: Sample route evaluation workflow

This has been applied to both rural and non-rural parts of the NCN restricted to each English UTLA. The outputs are tabulated in output CSV files, enabling England-wide analysis of whether each UTLA is appropriately served in a way representative of the population contained. It turns out that some UTLAs are entirely unserved, however many of these are sections of London, where UTLAs may be very small areas due

to the population density; furthermore, whilst such inner-city areas may not be served by the NCN, they may be served by other cycling infrastructure.

3.4 Assessing usage on the National Cycle Network

This section details two different approaches which were undertaken to assess the usage of the NCN. The first approach sought to explore the counter data provided by Sustrans and analyse temporal patterns. The second approach sought to explore the network usage data provided by Sustrans, evaluating how the different characteristics of network segments (such as quality of surface or provision of lighting) impacted the modelled usage of the network.

3.4.1 Insights from counter data

The analyses in this section display insights into how the count volumes recorded by counters on the NCN varies hourly, monthly and on weekdays vs weekends. The hourly and monthly count volumes have been aggregated for each category of property that the NCN section that the counter is on (e.g., lighting, quality) and by the demographic information within the NCN buffer for the UTLA that the counters are in (e.g., total household, percentage of household with no car or van) — an output of the previous section. Whilst this analysis focuses on a limited selection of demographic factors, the approach is illustrative of how it can be used for other demographic variables. It is hoped that such insights will provide information on the current usage of the NCN and for future developments.

Data processing We have created `.csv` files of monthly mean count volumes for the counter dataset described in Section 2.3.3. For each counter station, these files provide the monthly mean count volume for each hour of day, year and mode, aggregated by weekday (Monday to Friday) and weekend. Creating a monthly mean dataset of the counter data has the advantage of reducing data volume and minimising day-to-day variability due to factors such as weather conditions. The data has been grouped by weekday and weekend due to likely differences in

behaviour [Todd et al., 2021]. All count volumes that contained a value of “NA” in the original dataset have been excluded.

The latitude and longitude of each counter in the monthly mean files has been retrieved by linking them to the Sustrans counter ID number. The coordinate information of the counter is then used in identifying the NCN section that the counter is on. To link the counter location to the NCN section, first a buffer of 50 m (10 m was also tested) is placed around the NCN to account for any discrepancies in the exact location of the NCN. The counter and NCN dataset are joined when the counter coordinates intersects the NCN section. The spatial join enables the properties of the NCN segment (such as route number, quality, lighting) for each counter to be obtained.

The NCN section that each counter is on was then linked to the accessibility and demographic metrics within the NCN buffer zone as computed in Section 3.2. Each NCN segment has a corresponding identifier “FID”. The upper tier local authority (UTLA) that each NCN section (identified through FID) is in was used to obtain the accessibility and demographic information within the NCN buffer zone of the respective UTLA. We calculated the quartile ranges for each accessibility and demographic metric (detailed in the Statistical Analysis in Section 3.3.3) across the buffer zones of UTLAs that contain counters. In defining these quartile ranges, we divide the data into four equally sized sets. Given an ordered dataset, these quartiles are defined based on the following identifiers:

- *min*: The lowest datapoint.
- Q_1 : The datapoint which divides the smallest 25% of the data from the remainder of the data.
- Q_2 : The median; the data points which divides the lower half of the data from the higher half of the data.
- Q_3 : The datapoint which divides the largest 25% of the data from the remainder of the data.
- *max*: The highest datapoint.

Based on these identifying points in the data, we can then split the data into four groups:

- `low`: Datapoints which lie between *min* and Q_1 .
- `med_low`: Datapoints which lie between Q_1 and Q_2 .
- `med_high`: Datapoints which lie between Q_2 and Q_3 .
- `high`: Datapoints which lie between Q_3 and *max*.

If we specifically consider splitting data based on the proportion of households without a car or van, we are able to split the UTLAs into equally sized subsets labelled as above where the `high` group represents the UTLAs where the largest proportion of households are without a car or van, and the `low` group represents the UTLAs where fewest households are without a car or van. By considering which of these four types of UTLAs the counters lie within, we can explore how car/van ownership impacts the variation in the volume of users of the NCN in these areas.

Seaborn lineplots were used to produce visualisation of count volumes. The count volumes have been aggregated by NCN section properties and the accessibility/demographic data. The lineplot aggregates across the data from multiple counter stations by calculating the mean and 95% confidence intervals. As a result, when the number of counter stations in some categories are very low, the count volume may appear erroneous compared to categories with a larger data sample. Due to some counter stations recording daily counts at 00:00 hours, this hour has been excluded in the hourly plots shown below.

Hourly variation in count volume aggregated by NCN properties

This sub-section shows examples of hourly count volumes of cyclists in 2019 (change if using other years) when the counter locations are aggregated by attributes of the NCN section they are on.

Figure 17 shows the hourly variation in usage of the NCN during the week with peaks corresponding to normal commuting times. In addition, the visualisation suggests that the Monday-Friday count volume on sections of the NCN that are of good quality and fully lit is higher than other sections. Whilst improved conditions may correlate with and increase in the count volume on weekdays, we observed that the peaks still occur at commuting times, indicating that such factors may not result in people shifting their

(a) Quality

(b) Lighting

Figure 17: Weekday (Mon-Fri) cyclist count volumes for each hour in Jan and July 2019 at counters on the NCN. The count volume has been grouped by the NCN section properties (Lighting) and (Quality).

behaviour to use the infrastructure earlier in the morning or later in the evening for leisure. This appears to align with suggestions in the literature that “Cycle routes across large quiet parks or along canal towpaths may not be well used outside peak commuting times after dark, even if lighting is provided...” [Group, 2008, Fotios and Castleton, 2017]. It may be the case that sections that have increased lighting in urban areas are likely to draw a larger volume of users, particularly in the context of weekday commuting.

Figure 18 shows a corresponding count volume plot for the weekend. It appears the peak volume of cyclists at counter locations is lower at the weekends compared to weekdays. Just as in the case of weekday data, we observe here that poor surface quality correlates with reduced count volumes. Whilst there is not a large difference between the count volumes observed for the different lighting conditions, it is noticeable that the less well lit sections receive higher count volumes in Summer than in Winter — this can be observed by comparing the subplots in Figure 18b.

Monthly variation aggregated by NCN properties Figure 19 shows the monthly variation in count volume on the NCN when aggregated by lighting. The plot shows a seasonal dependence of count volume, with higher count volumes during the Summer months and lower count volumes during the Winter months, both on weekends and weekdays. On weekends, there is little variation in monthly count volumes across the different lighting conditions; on weekdays, however, we can observe that monthly count volumes depend on lighting conditions with improved lighting corresponding to increased count volumes across the year. Again, when specifically focusing on the counts observed on weekends across the year, we notice that fully lit sections receive relatively consistent volumes of cyclists over the course of the year. In the case of partially lit and unlit sections, however, we find that there are more significant variations over the course of the year with higher volumes being observed in Summer and Lower volumes being observed in Winter.

If we assume that more *leisure* cycling occurs on the weekends, we may hypothesise that leisure cycling is more influenced by the provision of lighting. As was observed previously (when discussing the impact of

(a) Quality

(b) Lighting

Figure 18: Weekend cyclist count volume for each hour in Jan and July 2019 at counters on the NCN. The count volume has been grouped by the NCN section properties (Lighting) and (Quality).

Figure 19: Monthly cyclist count volume for 2019 at counters on the NCN. The count volume has been grouped by the NCN section properties (Lighting).

lighting on hourly counts), it is likely that there is a correlation between the provision of lighting and whether a section is in an urban setting; this then suggests that cyclists may undertake leisure cycling on unlit and partially lit sections of the network in more rural settings over the Summer months when there are longer daylight hours, but may not feel comfortable doing this in the Winter when daylight hours are shorter.

Linking count data with accessibility and demographic data from the access point and buffer analyses The analyses on identifying access points and improving the spatial buffer around the NCN described in Section 3.2 allowed us to visualise the count volume aggregated by the accessibility and demographic statistics. These were computed within the NCN buffer zone for the UTLA that each NCN segment with a counter was in.

Figure 20 shows an example of the weekday cycle count volume aggregated by the number of total households, percentage of households without a car or van and access percentage within the buffer zone of the NCN in each UTLA. The access percentage refers to the area from the isochrone buffer method compared to the crude buffer method, i.e., the ratio defined in Equation 1. The figure is an example of insights available from the accessibility and demographic information calculated in the Data

(a) Total households

(b) Non-car or van households

(c) Access percentage

Figure 20: Weekday cyclist count volume for July 2019 at counters on the NCN. The count volume has been grouped by the accessibility and demographic statistics in the NCN buffer zone (at 500 m) for the UTLA that the counter is in.

Study Group. In Figure 20a, we see that the lowest quartile for the number of households received the lowest count volumes — something that we would expect. In Figure 20b, we see that the lowest quartile for the percentage of households without a car or van also received lower count volumes. This quartile represents areas where households are more likely to have access to a motorised vehicle and consequently we may expect the population in these areas to choose these vehicles as their mode of transport for commuting (with a commuting pattern being clearly observed in the data); it is, therefore, unsurprising that these areas see reduced count volumes [Neves and Brand, 2019]. In areas where households are more likely to be without a motorised mode of transport, we observe increased count volumes.

3.4.2 Whole network usage estimates

To perform a comprehensive analysis of the impact of NCN characteristics on ‘predicted cycle trips’, we performed a spatial join of the WNUE dataset with the NCN dataset. This yielded 27 parameters that may affect our measured parameter. Our primary goal is to analyse the impact of various features on the target variable ‘predicted cycle trips’ and assess their statistical significance. Out of the 27 initial columns, we removed irrelevant columns such as IDs and geometry points, as well as columns with high proportions of missing values. The categorical columns, including Greenway, Surface, Quality, and Lighting, had low proportions of missing values, and we imputed the missing values using the modal values for each of the columns. Additionally, we identified null values in columns such as ‘Surface,’ ‘Quality,’ and ‘Route Category’ with values labelled as ‘N/A,’ which we dropped. After removing the non-essential columns, we were left with 11 features for our target variable. We performed dimensionality reduction on these features to evaluate their significance and performed linear regression to analyse the impact of coefficients for each variable and determine if a linear model is appropriate.

Dimensionality Reduction Since we are dealing with categorical and numerical values, we use the Factorial Analysis of Mixed Data (FAMD) algorithm. FAMD is a statistical technique used to analyse complex

datasets that contain both categorical and numerical variables. It is a type of dimensionality reduction method that helps identify and extract the most critical features of the data using an approach similar to principal component analysis (PCA). The logic behind FAMD is to create a new set of variables (or dimensions) that represent the most significant information contained in the original data. These dimensions are derived by combining the original variables in a way that explains the greatest degree of variability of the data while preserving the relationships between variables.

Whilst PCA is often used, it is constrained by being targeted for use with numerical variables [Abdi and Williams, 2010]; in cases where we have only categorical data, we may use Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) [Abdi and Valentin, 2007]. In this case, however, we are dealing with “mixed data”, i.e., data containing both categorical and numerical variables. This is a task for which FAMD is suited. It converts the categorical variables into numerical form, which creates a set of binary variables that represent the different categories of the original categorical variable. To perform FAMD on our data, we use the Prince library in Python [Halford].

Once the data have been transformed, FAMD uses PCA to extract the most important dimensions that capture the majority of the variability in the data. These dimensions can then be used for visualisation or further analysis. FAMD also provides statistical measures that allow you to interpret the importance of each variable in the analysis.

For our dataset, Table 1 shows 11 predictor variables that might influence the outcome variable. Out of the predictor variables, six are categorical, three are numerical and two are Boolean.

When undertaking FAMD, we are required to specify how many components should be used. For this investigation, 5 components were chosen to strike a balance between amount of variance explained by each component and the computational efficiency of the algorithm. In our case, the first 5 components explain a significant portion of the total variance.

Features	Description	Type
Desc	Description of the route - On road, Ferry or Traffic free	Categorical
Greenway	Whether greenpath or not	Categorical
RouteType	Type of route - NCN, RCN or a Link	Categorical
Surface	Type of Surface (explained in section 2.2.2)	Categorical
Quality	Surface quality (explained in section 2.2.2)	Categorical
Lighting	Whether the path is fully lit, partially lit or unlit	Categorical
Factor On Road	Whether the WNUE section is on-road or off-road	Boolean
Actual cycle count	Whether the count is actual or estimated	Boolean
Year	Year of usage estimation	Numerical
Population Gravity	Population density in 10 km of section radius (explained in section 2.2.2)	Numerical
Cycle to work gravity	Level of cycle to work in 10 km radius of the section (explained in section 2.2.2)	Numerical

Table 1: Features with description for WNUE and NCN Characteristics

Results Tables 4, 5 and 6 show the outputs, in which each row represents a variable in the original dataset, while each column represents a principal component. These are supplied as an appendix as a result of the volume of information provided. The numbers in the cells represent the contributions of the corresponding variables to each principal component. The higher the value, the more important the variable is in that component. Two example rows are provided below in Table 2. These rows show the contributions of the two categories of ON ROAD to each of the five components.

Variable	comp0	comp1	comp2	comp3	comp4
factor ON ROAD False	1.312e-01	3.065e-02	1.353e-03	7.780e-05	9.328e-04
factor ON ROAD True	1.409e-01	3.292e-02	1.453e-03	8.357e-05	1.002e-03

Table 2: Example of FAMD Coefficients for `factor ON ROAD` Categories for Five Components (comp0 — comp4). Contributions to components provided in standard form to 3 decimal places.

To determine which variables should be reduced based on this output, we used the following steps:

1. Look for variables that have low values across all components. These variables are not contributing much to the overall variance in the dataset and can be considered for removal.
2. Identify variables that have high values in only one or two components. These variables may be considered for removal if they are not important in the analysis or if they are redundant with other variables.
3. Keep variables that have high values in multiple components. These variables are contributing to the overall variance in the dataset and are important for the analysis.

Based on these steps, the following variables were considered for removal:

- **Greenway No:** This variable has low values in all components except for component 3, where it has a relatively high value. This suggests that it is not contributing much to the overall variance in the dataset and may be redundant with other variables.
- **Quality MTBOnly:** This variable has a very high value in component 3, but low values in all other components. This suggests that it is not contributing much to the overall variance in the dataset and may be considered for removal.
- **RouteType LINK:** This variable has a relatively high value in component 2, but low values in all other components. This suggests that it is not contributing much to the overall variance in the dataset and may be considered for removal.
- **Surface Other:** This variable has low values in all components except for component 4, where it has a relatively high value. This suggests that it is not contributing much to the overall variance in the dataset and may be redundant with other variables.

When conducting dimensionality reduction analysis, we found that the following variables had high values in at least one of the components (as shown in Tables 4–6) and as such propose that they be kept:

- Desc OnRoad
- Desc TrafficFree
- Surface UnsealedFirm
- Quality Rough
- Lighting FullLit
- Lighting NotLit
- Surface BareEarth
- Quality Acceptable
- Surface Rocky

Our dimensionality reduction analysis suggests removing the 'Route Type' column and dropping rows associated with 'MTBOnly' and 'Surface Other'. We can also analyse the data with and without the 'Greenway' variable.

Linear Regression We performed an ordinary least squares linear regression on our data to understand the linear effect of various independent variables in Table 1 on the dependant variable — the logarithm of ‘predicted cycle trips’. The summary table in figure 25 shows the results of a linear regression model using the `statsmodel.api` library in Python [Seabold and Perktold, 2010] to predict the number of cycling trips based on the independent variables. The R -squared value of 0.063 indicates that 6.3% of the variance in cycling trips can be explained by the independent variables in the model. The Adjusted R -squared value is similar, indicating that there is no significant improvement in model fit by adding more variables. The F -statistic of 243.3 and its associated probability value of 0.00 suggest that the overall model is statistically significant, meaning that at least one of the independent variables is related to the number of cycling trips.

Figure 26 shows the coefficients for each independent variable. The coefficients represent the amount of change in the dependent variable associated with a one-unit change in that independent variable, all other variables being held constant. For example, a one-unit increase in ‘WNUE population grav’ (which is measured in thousands) is associated with a decrease of 0.0355 in the predicted number of cycling trips.

Some variables have positive coefficients, indicating a positive relationship with the dependent variable, while others have negative coefficients, indicating a negative relationship. For example, the coefficient for actual cycle count is 0.1182, indicating that a one-unit increase in actual cycle count is associated with an increase of 0.1182 in the logarithm of the predicted number of cycling trips.

A p -value less than 0.05 suggests that the coefficient is statistically significant and can be considered as evidence against the null hypothesis. For example, the p -values for all of the Surface variables are less than 0.05, indicating that each of them is significantly related to the number of cycling trips.

As an extension to this analysis, it would be worth understanding how interactions between the predictor variables impact the response variable; such variable interactions may be specified using generalised linear models. We can create two-four models with interactions of two variables at a time and three variables at a time. This would give more insight into

the effect of the combination of factors on the dependant variable. For instance, how the predicted cycle trips is impacted for the combination of a route having an asphalt surface, acceptable quality and a fully lit path.

3.5 Analysis of survey data

To minimise the loss of information due to data quality issues, data processing was done before performing analyses on the processed survey data.

For the purpose of analysis, some of the key groups were taken into focus for this study -

- Demographics
 - Gender
 - Ethnicity
 - Age
 - Disability
- Accessibility to different resources
 - Work/Education
 - Services/Shops
 - Recreation/Social
 - Other

3.5.1 Data pre-processing

Since the survey data is unstructured, some data pre-processing was performed to normalise the variables in focus, and make it usable for further analysis without losing much information across the different variables. Much of this was achieved by regrouping categorical variable values as outlined below (and as can be found in Table 3).

Before changes	After changes
Accessibility	
Education Work	Education/Work
Health Public Shops Transport	Services/Shops
Family & Friends Nature Tourist Attraction	Recreation/Social
Other	Other
Ethnicity	
African Black Caribbean	African, Caribbean or Black
mixed / Mixed	Mixed
other / Other Arab	Other
Indian	Indian
Chinese	Chinese
Pakistani	Pakistani
Bangladeshi Tamil Asian	Asian
Age	
16-24 / 18-24 25-34	Young
35-44 45-54 55-64	Middle-aged
65+	Elderly

Table 3: Table showing how variables were regrouped.

Re-coding of some variables Some of the variables had different labelling, possibly from a particular survey structure used before. These values were re-coded to meet the general standard of labelling used in the other variables providing the same information.

Joining all the similar variables together One of the factors covered in the surveys was the accessibility of types of locations (e.g. education, work, etc.). For each of these, there were multiple variables imparting the same information. All these similar variables were combined together into another variable. No intersection was observed between these multi-variables. They were then re-coded to 0/1, implying the absence and presence of the accessibility resource respectively, in that region.

Re-grouping of the categories in demographics and accessibility variables As Table 3 illustrates, some of the variables were re-grouped to ensure that most of the information from the surveys was preserved. The necessity of this step is to standardise most of the categories, since many of the categories changed over the different surveys. Generally, it was observed that the surveys with a greater number of respondents had more granular level of categorisation, while others had fewer. For example, for the age variable, one of the surveys had only two categories (18-64 and 64+). These differences hindered the analysis. Furthermore, some of the larger communities were maintained to ensure proper representation, such as Indian, Chinese and Pakistani; in other cases, some were merged with others because of the lack of data points, such as combining Arab with others.

Creating a count table of the grouped accessibilities To check the level of accessibility of different resources, a binary count table of all the accesses were created based on the different demographics of interest. The level ranged from 'None' (access to none of the four categories of amenities) to 'All' (access to all the four categories of amenities); between these two ends of the spectrum, there were entries for the intersections of access to different resources.

3.5.2 Insights from the data

Having outlined the transformations that were undertaken to standardise the data, this section outlines some of the insights that were derived from the survey data.

Percentage of accessibility to resources based on age and gender

Figure 21 shows the which resources respondents feel they have access to and how this varies with age and gender. Figure 21 shows that most of the respondents do not have access to any of the resources. Yet for the people who do have access to some of the resources, they tend to prefer staying closer to places nearer to their workplace or education institute, or shops/services. These two accessibility resources seem to dominate over the other ones, especially with younger and middle-aged generations. But the elderly people of both genders have an overall lesser accessibility to most of the resources. It can be seen that elderly people have lesser access to education or work amenities; this is not surprising as many of them will likely be retired and therefore are unlikely to require access to these resources. However, they also appear to be disadvantaged with regards to access to the other essentials with the exception of access to either shops/services or social resources only.

Percentage of accessibility to resources for disabled people based on age and gender

Following on from this, we are able to focus more specifically on respondents who are disabled as seen in Figure 22. Figure 22 shows that most of the disabled people have lesser access to most of the resources, but there exists visible differences among the respondents based on their gender. Disabled men are observed to have lesser access to any of the resources. Younger disabled women seems to have a much better access to any/most of the resources as compared to their male counterparts, and yet the elderly disabled women have close to no access to most of the resources. In terms of resources, work/education is seen to be the most popular aside from shops/services.

Access to amenities based on ethnicity and gender Figure 23 illustrates the level of accessibility to the different resources based on

Figure 21: Barplot showing the proportion of the respondents having access to different amenities. The different colours of the bars indicate different age-groups, while the two columns specify for each of the two genders.

Figure 22: Barplot showing showing proportion of the disabled respondents having access to different amenities. The different colours of the bars indicate different age-groups, while the two columns specify for each of the two genders.

different ethnic minorities. As an initial step, the proportion of white and non-white ethnic backgrounds were compared among the respondents. Since it was observed that almost 90% of the respondents were White, it was decided to focus only on the ethnic minorities as they were under-represented. Only a small portion of the respondents were from non-white ethnic backgrounds, which explains why many of the communities as seen in the table are under-represented in terms of accessibility to resources.

An overall assessment shows that most of the people from these communities have no access to any of the resources at all. In some communities, women seem to have comparable accessibility to either services/shops, education/work or socials, while men are seen to have more access to work/education than the other two. In the 'Other' minority group, women are seen to have much less accessibility as a much smaller proportion could only access Services and Socials only. In many cases of them do not have access to more than two resources at a time. This may suggest an over lack of accessibility for these communities.

Figure 24 further adds to the previous points, and shows a notable differences in accessibility to resources between the two genders. Such an approach can be used to further explore the issues of accessibility and how they vary with regards to both ethnicity and gender.

3.5.3 Limitations

When considering the analysis of the survey data, we should take into account the following potential biases and limitations:

- **Locations of surveys:** Each survey was undertaken in a geographical location, and as such the responses can only be considered representative of those locations and cannot necessarily be generalised.
- **Unequal representation of the respondents:** In some cases, surveys may have been undertaken with a focus on specific demographic groups.

Asian			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	None	85.710000	81.250000
1	Services & Education/Work	3.570000	6.250000
2	Services only	10.710000	6.250000
3	Social only	0.000000	6.250000

(a) Asian

Caribbean, African or Black			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	None	80.950000	91.430000
1	Services & Education/Work	7.140000	0.000000
2	Services & Others	2.380000	0.000000
3	Services & Social	0.000000	5.710000
4	Services only	4.760000	2.860000
5	Services, Education/Work & Social	2.380000	0.000000
6	Social only	2.380000	0.000000

(b) Caribbean, African or Black

Indian			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	Education/Work & Social	4.760000	7.690000
1	Education/Work only	4.760000	0.000000
2	None	89.050000	84.620000
3	Others only	2.380000	0.000000
4	Services only	4.760000	0.000000
5	Services, Education/Work & Social	9.520000	7.690000
6	Social only	4.760000	0.000000

(c) Indian

Chinese			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	Education/Work & Others	10.000000	0.000000
1	Education/Work only	0.000000	10.000000
2	None	80.000000	60.000000
3	Services & Education/Work	0.000000	10.000000
4	Services, Education/Work & Social	10.000000	10.000000
5	Social & Others	0.000000	10.000000

(d) Chinese

Pakistani			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	None	33.330000	60.000000
1	Others only	11.110000	0.000000
2	Services & Education/Work	11.110000	0.000000
3	Services & Social	11.110000	0.000000
4	Services, Education/Work & Social	33.330000	20.000000
5	Social only	0.000000	20.000000

(e) Pakistani

Other			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	Education/Work & Social	5.880000	0.000000
1	None	47.060000	80.000000
2	Services & Social	5.880000	0.000000
3	Services only	5.880000	0.000000
4	Services, Education/Work & Social	23.530000	0.000000
5	Social only	11.760000	20.000000

(f) Other

Mixed			
	Accesses	Men	Women
0	None	100.000000	66.670000
1	Services only	0.000000	22.220000
2	Services, Education/Work & Social	0.000000	11.110000

(g) Mixed

Figure 23: Tables showing accessibility to different resources by the ethnic minorities in the surveyed regions; values show percentage of group with access to the given resource.

Figure 24: Barplot showing showing proportion of the respondents having access to different amenities. The different colours of the bars indicate different (non-white) ethnicities, while the two columns specify for each of the two genders.

- **Inconsistency in granularity of categorisation in variables:** As mentioned in the previous section, the different granularity in the categories of some variables (possibly due to scale of the respective survey) hindered efficient re-grouping of some of the variables. A standard approach could be used in the future for data collection, even with different scales of the surveys.

4 Future work and research avenues

Over the course of the investigation, a number of ideas were presented for how to address the objectives presented in Section 1.2, and how the work presented here could be expanded upon. This section seeks to outline some the ideas for future work and recommended research avenues.

4.1 Improving identification and segmentation of the NCN

As noted in Section 2.3, some issues arose during the investigation regarding inconsistent IDs across different datasets, which presented a challenge when looking to work with joined datasets. While different datasets had ID numbers for different segments of the NCN, they are not consistent or of a similar format between the datasets and not necessarily guaranteed to be the same in the same dataset as identifiers for segments change over time. Additionally, the segment IDs in the publicly available map were used for audit purposes, and thus often change if one of the variables (e.g. surface type) changes, instead of being based on logical partitions of the route. One suggested improvement to the data that would aid future analysis would be to have consistent identifiers for segments of the NCN and for larger partitions (many of which may have pre-existing names) to be identified; this would help with regards to consistency of publicly available map downloads and re-usability of historical audit and analysis data. Formally, this appears to be a slowly changing dimension engineering problem, very similar to that used for geographies (e.g. LSOAs are mapped to LTLAs, but both LSOAs and LTLAs can be created, destroyed, merged or renamed over time).

4.2 Identifying informal access points

Identifying informal access points to the NCN was an objective of the challenge that we explored in Section 3.1.2, but did not find a solution to. If a GPS heatmap dataset becomes openly available it could be used to find access points that are not on the road or footpath network in OSMs. Visual satellite imagery may have potential to be used to locate informal

access points. However, we did not explore the avenue further due to the time constraints of the challenge.

4.3 Agent-based modelling analysis

When proposing the installation of new routes and infrastructure, we may be particularly interested in how it would be used and might impact traffic flow, for instance through diverting active travel away from congested roads. One avenue through which this could be explored is using Agent-based modelling [[Kagho et al., 2020](#)]. Whilst the development of detailed Agent-based models can be a long process, some tools already exist for this purpose such as A/B Street ⁴. Agent-based approaches simulate systems at an individual-level, allowing us to explore the impact of policy changes in a disaggregated manner; this would allow us to explore the distributional ramifications of such changes.

One of the keys to the success of this method is a well-formulated set of characteristics for the agents in the simulation — this may present a challenge. Given the potential difficulty of obtaining volumes of individual-level data, generate synthetic demographic population data; this can be achieved using datasets such as the Census with a method called Spatial Microsimulation [[Lovelace et al., 2014](#)].

4.4 Statistical analysis of NCN usage

This investigation has outlined the development of a novel approach to producing buffers around the NCN. The figures of count volume aggregated by NCN properties, accessibility and demographics within buffer zones shown in Section 3.4.1 provide insights into the usage of the NCN; however, this focused on a very limited set of demographic factors — it is recommended that other factors be explored in a similar manner. Further visualisation and a statistical analysis could be produced to provide robust values on the dependence of NCN usage on these metrics.

⁴[A/B Street codebase](#)

4.5 Further Counter Data Analysis

This investigation undertook some analysis of the temporal patterns in the counter data. Some further avenues for exploration on this front may include:

- Geospatial analysis of counter data, e.g. using Spatial Autocorrelation and Geographically Weighted Regression to explore how spatially varying factors impact the volume of users on the network [Comber et al., 2023]. These approaches may be used to inform the location of new counters.
- Further analysis of time-series from counters, e.g. using changepoint analysis [Taylor, 2000] or interrupted time series analysis [Bernal et al., 2017] to explore whether there are significant changes in usage measured at counters near locations of changes in infrastructure.

5 Team members

Aditi Dutta is a PhD candidate at the University of Exeter (Q-Step), researching on online misogyny using social science and computational methods. She contributed to this project by exploring the survey data and making inferences based on the analysis, alongside writing and reviewing on the corresponding portions of the report. She was also one of the facilitators in the project.

Amy Peace is a climate scientist working on projects related to climate change adaptation and mitigation, with a background in research focused on aerosols-climate interactions. She contributed to this project by exploring informal access points to, and analysing usage on the National Cycle Network, plus writing and reviewing the report.

Cong Chen is a data engineer at Genomics England with a data science background working in health and life sciences after mathematical research in logic and model theory of graphs. He contributed to this project by writing and reviewing the report, reviewing data and linkage, developing analytical metrics and algorithms for graph and geometry manipulation and implementing them in Python, and engineering processes to compute statistics across the network.

Keiran Suchak is a Postdoctoral Research Fellow at the Institute for Transport Studies (University of Leeds). His research focuses on the development of methods for exploring the interaction between changes in transport policy and health, specifically focusing on the use of Agent-Based Models. He was the Principal Investigator for this project.

Poonam Brar is a data scientist and a post-graduate in Applied Data Science and Statistics from the University of Exeter. She contributed to this project by performing exploratory data analysis on the National Cycle Network usage by cyclists and implementing dimensionality reduction and linear regression methods to understand the effect of network path characteristics on the cyclists' frequency. She also contributed to writing and reviewing the report. She was the co-facilitator of the project.

Sivasharmini Ganeshamoorthy is a PhD student studying at Coventry University in the Centre for Computational Science and Mathematical

Modelling. Her research is related to computational biology. In this project she worked on analysing annual usage for pedestrians using National Cycle Network data.

Members of the Sustrans Research and Monitoring team supported the Data Study Group with data and methods developed by Sustrans, please contact monitoring@sustrans.org.uk for any questions about Sustrans work with data.

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A Supplementary Figures and Tables

```
=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          predict_trips_cyc    R-squared:                0.063
Model:                  OLS                 Adj. R-squared:           0.062
Method:                 Least Squares       F-statistic:              243.3
Date:                   Thu, 02 Mar 2023    Prob (F-statistic):       0.00
Time:                   19:22:24           Log-Likelihood:           19173.
No. Observations:      105632             AIC:                     -3.829e+04
Df Residuals:          105602             BIC:                     -3.800e+04
Df Model:               29
Covariance Type:       nonrobust
```

Figure 25: Summary Statistics for the Linear Regression Model

Variable	0	1	2	3	4
WNUE	8.389e-04	3.217e-02	4.569e-04	1.886e-03	1.310e-03
pop grav uncapped					
WNUE	1.983e-04	2.041e-02	1.835e-04	1.463e-03	1.274e-04
ctw perc grav uncapped					
WNUE	7.610e-05	2.463e-04	1.707e-05	9.662e-06	1.199e-04
year					
Desc	6.612e-09	1.684e-05	7.423e-04	4.044e-03	4.709e-02
Ferry					
Desc	1.429e-01	3.204e-02	1.436e-03	6.157e-05	8.794e-04
OnRoad					
Desc	1.331e-01	2.986e-02	1.316e-03	4.748e-05	6.912e-04
TrafficFree					
Greenway	7.405e-02	1.817e-05	6.986e-07	1.157e-03	4.815e-04
No					
Greenway	1.406e-01	3.450e-05	1.326e-06	2.196e-03	9.141e-04
Yes					
Lighting	1.294e-02	1.073e-01	1.047e-03	1.787e-02	6.796e-03
FullLit					
Lighting	1.093e-02	1.252e-01	2.103e-03	1.818e-02	2.650e-03
NotLit					
Lighting	1.014e-03	3.582e-02	1.510e-03	3.549e-03	4.499e-02
PartLit					
actual	1.779e-06	8.401e-06	5.854e-04	2.524e-06	2.419e-07
ped count					
False					
actual	1.426e-03	6.735e-03	4.693e-01	2.034e-03	1.939e-04
ped count					
True					

Table 4: FAMD Coefficients for all Variable Categories for Five Components (Part 1). Contributions to components provided in standard form to 3 decimal places.

Variable	0	1	2	3	4
RouteType LINK	2.064e-03	4.569e-02	3.916e-03	3.017e-02	1.278e-02
RouteType NCN	6.449e-05	3.598e-03	4.269e-04	3.422e-03	5.807e-04
RouteType RCN	1.350e-03	5.092e-03	4.508e-05	1.793e-04	8.582e-02
actual cyc count False	2.571e-06	4.651e-05	2.866e-03	1.202e-05	1.517e-05
actual cyc count True	4.449e-04	8.048e-03	4.960e-01	2.081e-03	2.625e-03
Surface Asphalt	2.234e-02	7.033e-03	1.105e-05	6.368e-04	9.663e-03
Surface BareEarth	1.078e-02	2.537e-02	3.113e-04	9.402e-02	1.526e-02
Surface Blocks	9.950e-04	2.143e-02	4.222e-04	1.542e-03	5.966e-03
Surface Cobbles	9.004e-04	6.468e-04	1.096e-03	4.969e-05	6.048e-02
Surface Concrete	4.517e-03	2.916e-04	5.117e-04	5.321e-03	1.476e-01
Surface Grass	1.579e-03	5.200e-03	2.629e-03	3.352e-02	2.244e-02
Surface Other	5.579e-03	1.426e-03	1.022e-03	8.248e-03	5.555e-02
Surface PavementSlabs	2.868e-03	4.363e-02	3.192e-03	4.590e-03	4.103e-02
Surface Rocky	5.021e-03	3.509e-02	4.303e-05	2.934e-01	9.676e-03
Surface Unknown	6.410e-06	6.027e-05	3.614e-04	4.298e-07	2.370-e02

Table 5: FAMD Coefficients for all Variable Categories for Five Components (Part 2). Contributions to components provided in standard form to 3 decimal places.

Variable	0	1	2	3	4
Surface Unsealed Firm	2.101e-06	9.879e-06	7.080e-08	8.491e-05	1.017e-02
Surface Unsealed Firm	7.070e-02	6.463e-02	2.051e-03	7.266e-02	2.345e-03
Surface Unsealed Loose	1.545e-02	3.942e-02	1.647e-03	2.069e-04	4.636e-02
Quality Acceptable	7.447e-03	1.612e-02	3.369e-05	7.257e-02	1.734e-01
Quality MTB Only	1.435e-02	6.323e-02	7.366e-05	3.160e-01	4.045e-02
Quality Rough	2.438e-02	9.946e-02	1.778e-03	4.465e-04	8.027e-02
Quality Smooth	4.222e-03	4.498e-02	1.229e-06	1.126e-03	2.306e-02
Quality Standard	1.477e-02	1.606e-02	4.174e-05	7.075e-03	2.253e-02
factor ON ROAD False	1.312e-01	3.065e-02	1.353e-03	7.780e-05	9.328e-04
factor ON ROAD True	1.409e-01	3.292e-02	1.453e-03	8.357e-05	1.002e-03

Table 6: FAMD Coefficients for all Variable Categories for Five Components (Part 3). Contributions to components provided in standard form to 3 decimal places.

coef	std err	t	P> t	[0.025	0.975]
17.7885	0.587	30.329	0.000	16.639	18.938
-0.0355	0.003	-11.817	0.000	-0.041	-0.030
0.4576	0.012	38.644	0.000	0.434	0.481
-0.0598	0.005	-12.927	0.000	-0.069	-0.051
0.1182	0.009	12.700	0.000	0.100	0.136
-0.0193	0.020	-0.986	0.324	-0.058	0.019
-0.0234	0.001	-28.970	0.000	-0.025	-0.022
6.0059	0.202	29.729	0.000	5.610	6.402
5.9077	0.197	30.057	0.000	5.522	6.293
5.8749	0.197	29.891	0.000	5.490	6.260
8.8900	0.293	30.315	0.000	8.315	9.465
8.8986	0.293	30.343	0.000	8.324	9.473
5.9069	0.195	30.215	0.000	5.524	6.290
5.9396	0.196	30.379	0.000	5.556	6.323
5.9420	0.196	30.391	0.000	5.559	6.325
1.3914	0.048	29.151	0.000	1.298	1.485
1.3640	0.048	28.308	0.000	1.270	1.458
1.3379	0.048	27.892	0.000	1.244	1.432
1.3000	0.049	26.757	0.000	1.205	1.395
1.3112	0.048	27.297	0.000	1.217	1.405
1.3235	0.051	26.094	0.000	1.224	1.423
1.2397	0.048	25.722	0.000	1.145	1.334
1.3445	0.048	28.010	0.000	1.250	1.439
1.3867	0.049	28.248	0.000	1.290	1.483
1.4568	0.192	7.582	0.000	1.080	1.833
1.5493	0.068	22.785	0.000	1.416	1.683
1.4065	0.048	29.454	0.000	1.313	1.500
1.3770	0.048	28.701	0.000	1.283	1.471
3.5454	0.117	30.221	0.000	3.315	3.775
3.5899	0.117	30.557	0.000	3.360	3.820
3.5482	0.117	30.239	0.000	3.318	3.778
3.5589	0.117	30.330	0.000	3.329	3.789
3.5461	0.117	30.228	0.000	3.316	3.776
5.9206	0.196	30.282	0.000	5.537	6.304
5.9745	0.195	30.564	0.000	5.591	6.358
5.8935	0.196	30.141	0.000	5.510	6.277

Figure 26: Summary Statistics for the Coefficients of the Linear Regression Model

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